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Chemical Constituents of *Vallisneria spiralis*

O. Ktze

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THE latex obtained from *Vallisneria spiralis* O. Ktze (Apocyanaceae) is widely used as an anti-inflammatory agent in the treatment of old wounds and sores¹. Some phytochemical work on this plant is on record^{2,3,4}. The present note reports the isolation of some chemical constituents from its leaves.

The powdered airdried leaves of *V. spiralis* were extracted successively with petroleum ether and benzene in a Soxhlet. The petrol extract was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina and the benzene eluates upon concentration and cooling yielded a crystalline sterol m.p. 134-35°; acetate m.p. 126-28°; benzoate m.p. 141-43°. It was identified as β -sitosterol by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p. and IR) of the compound and its derivatives with the authentic samples.

The benzene extract on concentration and cooling separated a crystalline mass identified as potassium nitrate. The concentrated mass was chromatographed over Brockmann alumina and the petrol-benzene (10:2) eluates yielded a triterpene alcohol which crystallised from methanol as needles, m.p. 187-89°; IR (nujol) broad band between 3300-3400 cm^{-1} (-OH); acetate, m.p. 238-39° and benzoate m.p. 229-31°, suggesting its identity with β -amyrin which was further confirmed by direct comparison (m.p., m.m.p., co-TLC and IR) with authentic samples. The chloroform-methanol (1:6) eluates furnished a triterpene acid, m.p. 277-79°; IR (KBr) 3350-3450 cm^{-1} (-OH), 1685 cm^{-1} (C=O) and other peaks at 1380, 1370, 1350, 1305, 1270 and 1247 cm^{-1} characteristic of ursolic acid derivatives⁵. The mass spectrum showed besides molecular ion peak M^+ at m/e 456, prominent fragment ions at m/e 538(5%), 410(8%), 248(100%), 203(53%) and 133(53%) suggesting the compound to be ursolic acid. NMR (CDCl_3) exhibited signals for C-12 olefinic proton at δ 5.2, polymethylene envelope between δ 1.2-2.0 and seven methyl groups as singlets between δ 0.66-1.01. The compound formed a methyl ester, m.p. 169-70°. Finally, the identity of the compound with ursolic acid was confirmed by direct comparison with an authentic sample.

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Possible Antibacterial Compounds.

Synthesis of Alkyl penta-trans-2, trans-4 dienoic and Alkyl propyl-trans-2-enoic Acid Amides

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VARIOUS types of acid amide have been shown to be physiological active substances. Conjugated alkyl amides show significant insecticidal activity towards housefly¹. Many substituted toluamides have been shown to have antibacterial and insect repellent properties^{2,3}. In view of this it was thought of interest to synthesise various unsaturated alkyl amides.

The key reaction employed for the synthesis of various alkyl amides was modified Wittig reaction. Aliphatic aldehyde was submitted to modified Wittig reaction with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate or α -phosphonate of ethyl acetate to get the unsaturated esters. It has been shown that Wittig reaction of ylid enjoying resonance stabilization tend to be stereospecific and yield a great preponderance of trans product^{4,5}. This has been further proved to be so by spectral data of synthetic products. Various aldehydes such as heptaldehyde, palmitic aldehyde, citronellal and citral were used as starting material for the projected synthesis of various acid amide I to V. Typical procedure for the unsaturated acid amide was as follows.

Heptaldehyde was condensed with γ -phosphonate of ethyl crotonate in the presence of NaH using